

Fostering collaboration for open access publishing models: a study of the Polish ecosystem in the area of open access monographs in the humanities

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Open access and digital monographs are often perceived as less prestigious than traditionally printed books (Maryl et al. 2021). Open monographs - contrary to the journal publishing - have so far been on the margins of the digital and OA revolution in Poland (Morka and Gatti 2021). In general, due to the additional costs of preparing professional electronic publication formats (e.g. epub), publishing houses rarely publish scientific monographs in open access and they rather let authors publish their work under the license specified in the contract and after the embargo period (Adema and Rutten 2010). To strengthen the role of digital outputs in humanities we need to find and implement new sustainable models for publishers (Stone et al. 2021). The proposed paper will discuss the open access publishing ecosystem in Poland and its current challenges. It will be based on the study we will conduct in the upcoming 6 months to identify the main pain points in publishing open access monographs and possible ways in which a national-level collaborative model could help eliminate them.

Finding adequate sustainability models for those stakeholders requires close collaboration between publishers themselves as well as with infrastructure providers, decision makers in the ministry and libraries who are becoming one of the biggest actors in OA publishing (Karwasińska 2017). Maintenance of infrastructures, or simply speaking: digital tools and services facilitating scholarly communication, is certainly one of the biggest challenges from the economic point of view (Edmond 2020). However, the other demanding aspect is actually making truly useful, used and vivid tools, adjusting to stakeholders' needs and fulfilling them (Anderson 2013, van Zundert 2012). Appropriate methods need to be applied to identify the current practices of the publishers and to continue receiving feedback from them while prototypes of solutions are discussed and implemented.

In response to this situation Polish National Node for OPERAS is conducting research of Polish publishers' needs in the area of publishing open monographs. OPERAS is a European research infrastructure for the social sciences and humanities (SSH), (see here a number of publications about the consortium: <https://www.operas-eu.org/about/bookshelf/>). It has been established as a non-commercial initiative aimed at transforming the European research area of scholarly communication and therefore it is targeted at researchers, librarians, publishers and infrastructure providers in over a dozen of European countries. This rich and diverse group of stakeholders and the infrastructure's inclusive nature are the key to OPERAS's success (Maryl et al. 2020).

We will apply various approaches:

- Survey study - targeted at Polish publishers and editors it aimed at diagnosing the state of OA practices and crucial technological needs as well as shortcomings in collecting and analyzing metadata (such as keywords and references).
- Design thinking methods such as mind-mapping, value-proposition canvas, journey maps and affinity diagram (Design Thinking Methodology Book) will help us analyze the whole publishing process, map the main "pain points" and recognize usability issues restraining the industry from joining the OA community, that could be solved within right strategy and sustainability model.
- Workshop applying the design thinking method (Kimbell 2015) - through this technique publishers' needs will be recognised in order to formulate initial sustainability models for open access book publishing that will accommodate the specificity of Polish stakeholders. The design thinking workshop requires collaboration between publishers and other organizations: infrastructure providers, IT companies and libraries.
- Study on sustainability models in international academia - comparative analysis of current trends in OA publishing worldwide as well as diagnosis of needs and challenges for its development will bring insights on how OA publishing problems are tackled elsewhere.

The study will provide a comprehensive analysis of the current state of OA monographs publishing in the humanities in one of the EU countries. Additional results will be the reusable methodology of the study and recommendations for publishing houses. The paper is a part of the recently launched project funded by the Polish Ministry of Education and Science.

Bibliography

Adema, Janneke / Rutten, Paul (2010) Digital Monographs in the Humanities and Social Sciences: Report on User Needs.

Anderson, Sheila (2013) "What are Research Infrastructures?" in: International Journal of Humanities and Arts Computing, vol. 7 No. 1-2 4-23.

Edmond, Jennifer (2020) Digital Technology and the Practices of Humanities Research Cambridge: Open Book Publishers.

Karwasińska, Emilia (2017) „Biblioteczne usługi wydawnicze – nowa rola biblioteki naukowej” in: Komunikacja naukowa w humanistyce Poznań

Kimbell, Lucy (2011) "Rethinking Design Thinking: Part I" in: Design and Culture 3, 3:285-306. DOI: 10.2752/175470811X13071166525216.

Maryl, Maciej / Błaszczńska, Marta / Szulińska, Agnieszka / Rams, Paweł (2020) "The case for an inclusive scholarly communication infrastructure for social sciences and huma-

nities” [version 1; peer review: 2 approved] in: F1000Research, 9:1265. DOI:10.12688/f1000research.26545.1.

Morka, Agata / Rupert Gatti (2021) Academic Libraries and Open Access Books in Europe: A Landscape Study. DOI:10.21428/785a6451.f710a335.

Stone, Graham / Błaszczyńska, Marta / Lebon, Chloé / Morka, Agata / Mosterd, Tom / Mounier, Pierre / Proudman, Vanessa / Speicher, Lara / Melinščak Zlodi, Iva (2021) Collaborative Models for OA Book Publishers. DOI:10.5281/ZENODO.5494731.

Yayici, Emrah (2016) *Design Thinking Methodology Book*.

Van Zundert, Joris (2012) “If You Build It, Will We Come? Large Scale Digital Infrastructures as Dead End for Digital Humanities.” in: *Historical Social Research* 37, 3. DOI:10.12759/HSR.37.2012.3.165-186.